

Gender Support Plan

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Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

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Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: KTH
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1 Introduction

1.1 Background / Grant Agreement statements concerning gender balance:

- A fair gender representation (by promoting genuine equal access opportunities between men and women throughout the recruitment process) (Grant Agreement, page 41)
- The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level. (Grant Agreement, page 43)
- The network will have special focus on balance in gender representation. Science and computing in general have persistent gender inequality (40 %) and fields such as engineering, manufacturing and construction even more so (26 %). The InnoChain network decision making body has similar gender balance (24%) despite the coordinator being a woman. To support gender equality special emphasis will be made in inviting women visiting researchers as peer reviewers to evaluative research events, workshop-seminars and conference. Special focus on gender in the recruitment process will support appropriate gender balance in the ESR body and a Gender Support plan detailing family support and a mentoring programme will be part of the management agreement. (Annex to Grant Agreement, page 33)

2 Gender Balance of the Innochain network

2.1 Recruitment of ESRs – Early Stage Researchers

Female: 4

Male: 11

Percentage: W 27% M 73%

2.2 Management

- Steering Committee (SC)

Steering Committee (SC) consists of 7 members of which 2 women (M. Ramsgard Thomsen, U. Karlsson) and 5 men (J. Knippers, B. Sheil, M. Gausa, K. Bollinger, F. Scheurer)

Female: 2

Male: 5

- Supervisor Board (SB)

Supervisor Board (SB) consists of 7 members, 4 women (M. Ramsgard Thomsen, A. Jonkhans, A. Markopoulou, U. Karlsson) and 3 men (M. Tamke, B. Sheil, J. Knippers)

Female: 4

Male: 3

- Industry Board (IB)

Industry Board (IB) consists of 5 members (F. Scheurer, J. Runberger, M. Fleischmann, X. de Kestelier, S. Oesterle)

Male: 5

- Work Package Committee (WPC)

Work Packages Committee consists of 5 members, 2 woman (M. Ramsgard Thomsen, U. Karlsson) and 3 men (M. Gausa, B. Sheil, J. Knippers)

Female: 2

Male: 3

- Visiting scientists

Visiting scientists peers are (at the moment) 3, 1 woman (J. Sabin) and 2 men (M. Burry, M. Kohler)

Female: 1

Male: 2

3 Actions

3.1 Supervision

To strive for gender balance when engaging supervisors, second supervisors/assistant supervisors to ESR

3.2 Training events and conferences

To strive for gender balance when setting up, organizing and inviting guests and visiting researchers to training events and conferences:

Ex.:

Seminars

Workshop-seminars 1-4

Courses

Colloquia

Exhibitions

Conferences

Examinations

3.3 Assessment, peer-review, examination

To strive for gender balance when engaging researchers, industry partners to situations of evaluation and assessment

3.4 Management and network administration

To strive for gender balance amongst managerial and administrative personal

4 Goals

Goals are formulated to support and advance equality in research, and to support the balance of both genders in careers of research innovation.

4.1 Goals to support and advance equality in research

To take all steps required to maintain a proper and respectful *working environment* so that all researchers feel welcome and well integrated in the Innochain network and at the universities

To develop a *gender integrative platform* where strategies and actions respond to the experiences and needs of researchers at all levels in our group as they develop

To promote *self-direction*

To foster the careers of our researchers through guaranteed *personal skills training*, and support for *output* (publications, conferences, presentations, etc.).

To help communicate the experience of women researchers widely, both as promotion for the research theme and as *role models* for others

To encourage *young women researchers* to study in previously gender biased disciplines

To contribute actively to *increase the number of women researchers*, and commit to retain talented researchers and engage appropriate and excellent women at leadership levels

To be aware of the issue of equal opportunities within the broader research communities and industries associated with the Innochain program, and to use the Innochain platform as a venue to raise awareness of this issue with our varied stakeholders.